

METHODOLOGICAL FEATURES OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11190935>

Abstract: The article provides recommendations on easy and effective ways of using didactic games and songs related to the topic in the process of teaching English to preschool children, as well as on the formation of children's skills to participate in speech activities in a language other than their mother tongue.

Key words: Foreign language, language learning at an early age, educational game, activity, hand-eye coordination, types of active education, role-playing games.

Enter. Preschool education organization is not only the first step of continuous education, but also the first step in forming an active, creative and spiritually rich person. Currently, large-scale projects on teaching English are being implemented in state-owned and private pre-school educational institutions. It is desirable to teach foreign languages to children of preschool age to protect and strengthen their physical and mental health, and by carrying out one or another activity, children acquire a minimum communicative vocabulary sufficient to communicate in a foreign language in a simple way. One of the main conditions that ensure the effectiveness of education is the selection of educational content in order to encourage children's positive attitude to the English language and to use various educational tools and implement an active approach to teaching a foreign language. Among these tools, didactic games, which are considered an important component of pedagogical technology, occupy the main place. Also, the use of educational tools, songs related to small finger motor skills, and didactic games of a technological nature, which serve to create problem situations suitable for the subject of the training, are incomparable in ensuring the effectiveness of the lesson.

It became clear from the communication of teachers of preschool educational institutions in Uzbekistan that now foreign methodical manuals, books and computer programs are used to teach English to children. This can lead to a weakening of the attitude towards our national culture. Taking this into account, it is appropriate to organize lessons in preschool educational institutions that harmonize our national values and traditions in teaching English to children.

Children's attention, memory and perception can be formed without difficulty through the game. Because the child feels free during the game. The game also accepts data while playing. That is, the information provided through game activity is stored in children's memory without problems. In this case, learning English based on pedagogical, technological and physiological factors is a guarantee of results. As the students of preschool educational institutions learn English during the games, it is appropriate to follow the principles of presentation of information. Foreign language learning processes in preschool children are formed on the basis of social influences. It is forbidden by scientists that their attention,

memory, mental activity and communication, in many cases, depend on the effectiveness of external relations and game activities.

In the research on the method of organizing and conducting the English lesson through didactic games, its several stages are distinguished. Some researchers distinguish the following stages in the organization of games:

- a) preparation;
- b) organizational;
- c) game actions;
- g) final

These stages are fundamentally different from each other according to their characteristics, the time spent on the game, the independence of children and the activities of the educator.

In classes organized on the basis of modern information and communication technologies, students actively participate compared to ordinary classes, and the effectiveness of the English lesson increases. It should be taken into account that today's children are growing up in the era of advanced technologies, which allows them to fully use technical tools in the educational process. For this purpose, it is appropriate to teach English language to children in pre-school educational institutions in a way that is faithful to our national history and traditions through computer systems, radio, television, tape recorders and the Internet. The use of such advanced technologies will further develop the thinking of the next generation and encourage them to communicate in English. The introduction of modern information technologies in preschool educational organizations meets the current world standards, and also encourages the acquisition of quality knowledge of the English language on the basis of modern educational technologies. Taking English lessons in accordance with the needs of the times can stimulate the development of children's worldview. For this, the educator and pedagogue is required to take initiative, work on himself and use different methods, taking into account the age characteristics of children.

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